

Performance of some new rices in Chinsurah

S. K. Sinha and S. Biswas, Rice Research Station (RRS), Chinsurah, Hooghly 712102, India

We evaluated the performance of some new, high yielding rices in kharif and boro at RRS, Chinsurah (see table).

CN758-1-1-1, a longer duration variety, performed best in both seasons. BG367-7 and BG367-4 yielded well in kharif but not in boro. IR50 yielded well in both seasons, and has good grain type and short duration, which favor its use in a multiple cropping sequence.

Cold was a major constraint to IR50 in boro. Almost all IR50 seedlings turned yellow-brown and about 50% died of cold. The problem is being combatted by doubling the boro seed rate. Cold also increased seedling mortality after transplanting, but seedlings regained

Performance of rice varieties in kharif and boro at RRS, Chinsurah, India.

Variety	Seedling mortality ^a (%) in boro	Grain yield (t/ha)		Grain type
		kharif	boro	
CN758-1-1-1	0	5.5	5.8	Long slender
CN8341-1-3-7	0	4.8	4.3	Long slender
IR50	50	4.8	5.1	Long slender
BG361-7	0	5.1	4.2	Long bold
BG367-4	5	5.2	4.1	Long bold
IR9209-48-3-2	0	4.3	3.4	Long slender
HPU741	0	3.6	4.4	Long slender
KPG14	0	3.5	4.8	Long slender
IET6155	0	4.1	4.5	Long slender
IET6988	0	3.9	4.7	Medium slender
HPU71	0	3.6	3.4	Long slender

^a Seedling mortality in kharif was zero.

normal color as temperature increased during the growing season. BG367-7 and BG367-4 seedlings were slightly discolored, but seedling mortality was not significant. Cold did not affect seedlings of other varieties.

Varietal grouping by days to 50%

flowering showed no significant differences between IR50, BG367-7, BG367-4, and IR9209-48-3-2 in kharif, but days to 50% flowering changed in boro. Flowering of IR50, IET6988, and HPU71 was delayed in boro. BG367-7 and IET6155 flowered earlier in boro than in kharif. □

High yielding rices Paiyur 1 and PY1

K. Ganesan, W. W. Manuel, and C. K. Rajagopalan, Paddy Experiment Station (PES), Ambasamudram 627401, Tamil Nadu, India

We evaluated the yield potential of new rice varieties Paiyur 1 and PY1 at PES,

Ambasamudram, in 1981-82 and 1982-83. Paiyur 1 (IR1721-14/IR1330-3-3-2) and PY1 (IR8/Ponni) yielded 4.5 t/ha, 8% more than Mashuri, the locally popular high-yielding rice (Table 1, 2). Paiyur 1 and PY1 are tall with medium-slender white rice. They have been recommended for general cultivation in Tamil Nadu in Sep-Oct. □

Performance of IET7564, a short-duration culture

J. Venkatakrishnan, P. Vivekanandan, K. N. Pillai, and D. S. Aaron, Paddy Experiment Station (PES), Tirur 602025, Tamil Nadu, India

IET7564 (IRAT8/N22) is a 100-d variety developed at the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad. It has a medium-fine, white grain. It was tested at PES for suitability for sornavari season.

IET7564, IET7566, IET7613, and IET4786 were sown on 20 May 1983 transplanted on 17 Jun, and harvested in Sep. Checks were TKM9, IR50, ADT36, and PY2. NPK was applied at 100-50-50 kg/ha. TKM9 yielded highest and IET7564 lowest (see table). □

Table 1. Performance of Paiyur 1 at Ambasamudram, India.

Variety	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)			Flowering time (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/hill	Panicle Wt (g)
	1981-82		1982-83				
	MLT	ART					
Paiyur 1	5.2	4.3	3.9	105	123	5	1.7
IR20	3.1	3.3	2.8	97	89	5	1.3
Mashuri (Ponni)	4.4	3.9	4.0	105	124	6	1.4
Mean + SD	4.5						
CD (P= 0.05)		0.5	0.8				

^a MLT = multilocation trial, ART = adaptive research trial.

Table 2. Performance of PY1 at Ambasamudram, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)		Flowering time (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/hill	Panicle wt (g)
	1981-82	1982-83				
PY1	5.1	3.9	107	112	5	2.0
IR20	3.8	2.8	101	90	6	1.3
Mashuri (Ponni)	4.3	4.0	107	120	4	1.6
CD (P = 0.05)	0.8	0.8				

Grain yield and duration of rices grown in 1981 sornavari, Tirur, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)
TKM9	5.6	111
IR50	5.1	113
ADT36	5.0	117
IET4786	4.6	118
PY2	4.6	108
IET7566	4.0	113
IET7613	3.6	113
IET7564	2.6	100